

Impact of Black Money in India

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Abstract

Black money is refers to the funds earned on the black market; on which insure and other taxes have not paid or which is the process of criminal activity such as bribery kick backs and corruption. As for as Indian society the black income or money is an important evils source to the growth of the economy. It is should be controlled by the strict rules of the government. The resent steps of the central Government, demonization of the currency are one of the bold steps to control the black money in India. This papers aims to explain about to what are the source of black money, what are the effect and suggestions for the control of black money in India.

Keywords: Black income, money tax evasion, fiscal system.

What is Black Money

As we know that in the present times black money is used in our country up to a large extent so it is not possible for us to define it in a different way with different terms such as unaccounted income, black income, black wealth, underground wealth, or at economy level it is known as black economy, parallel economy, shadow economy, and unofficial economy. Therefore, all in all these terms usually refers to an income on which the taxes are imposed by government but have not been paid.

Black money refers to that money which is not fully legitimate property of the owner. It is normally received in terms of cash from economic activities. (i.e.) Individuals who received it must hide it, spend it on for the fulfillment of their needs.

According to National Institute of public Finance and Policy [NIPFP] defines

“Black money is the aggregate of incomes which are taxable but not reported to authorities”.

Apart from this, the term black money would also include legal income that is concealed or hide from public authorities:-

- To evade payment of taxes which includes – income tax, excise duty, sales tax, stamp duty etc.
- To evade payment of other governmental or statutory contributions.
- To evade compliance with the provisions of various industrial laws which exists such as the industrial dispute Act 1947, minimum wages Act 1948, payment of bonus Act 1965, Factories Act 1948
- To evade compliance with other laws and administrative procedures applicable in India.

Present status of Black Money in India

As we know, in the recent times the issue of Black Money and corruption has come into being with participation of our civil society and parliament institutions. In this context two main issues have come into being.

- Firstly, without an adequate factual basis, a large magnitude / amount of black money and unaccounted wealth stashed abroad every year.
- Secondly, Government, Response to address these issues has been inadequate or we say considerably negligible.

Reasons of generating Black Money

There are many reasons for the creation of black money in India. Some of them are as follows:-

(i) Controls and licensing systems

Black Money is increasing in India for the reasons of controls, permits, quotas and license.

(ii) Higher rates of Taxes

Higher rates of taxes has result growing tendency of tax evasion among the payers. Tax evasion is common in income tax, corporate tax, corporation tax, union excise duties, custom duties, sales tax etc.

(iii) Ineffective enforcement of tax laws

In India, the enforcement of tax laws in respect of income tax, sales tax, excise duty, stamp duty etc. is quite weak. This had led to enormous undertrained evasion of taxes and piling up of black money.

(iv) Funding of political parties

There is an upward tendency of supporting of political parties with the help of black money. Big trade houses are donating an enormous amount of black money to the political parties, especially the ruling party with the sole objective to tame the political leadership for deriving undue profit by manipulating policy decisions.

(v) Second world war after influences

During the time of Second World War, a lot of the Indian industry found circumstances favorable for black marketing supply industrial goods the traditional supplies of the west were cut-off, which resulted severe shortages in money essential fields.

(vi) Inflation

The addition in prices of commodities like petrol software products, etc. in international market, boost in prices of commodities due to high increase in duties and taxes imposed by the government, the conspicuous utilization created by people with unaccountable money, diverting resources from manufacture to speculation – all these is the root of inflation which in turn creates black money.

(vii) Agricultural Income

The reluctance to bring agricultural earnings in the realm of income tax has also contributed to creation of black money. Big industrial houses, over the past few decades have entered the agriculture sector in a big way by acquiring big farms.

(viii) Privatization

Privatization has opened up a new area to the private sector as well as to ministers and bureaucrats for making black money. It is expected that many seams come to light for making black money through privatization.

(ix) Transactions in Urban Real Estates

Real estate transaction is a significant source of generating black money in India.

(x) Other factors

Generation of black income in a country like India also results from other different activities like smuggling, property deals, bribery, kickbacks, commissions, concealment of income by professional, artists etc.

Objectives of the Study

- To know the present status of undisclosed income level in India.
- To study the main reason behind the generation of black money.
- To study the impacts of black money on Indian economy.

Generation of Black Money

It is generated through means of illegal activities.

- It is earned through illegal means such as drug trafficking, weapons trading, terrorism, selling counterfeit or stolen good etc.
- By corruption which includes bribe given to and by public officers.
- Hiding income through legal activities (i.e.) not reported to public authorities or we say to the government for the purpose to evade taxes.
- Even commercial classes generate black money through trade.

Review of Literature

Sukanta Sarkar (2010) conducted a study on the parallel economy in India causes, impacts and governments initiatives in which he focused on the existence of causes and impacts of black money in India. According to him, the main reason behind the generation of black money is the India political system. (i.e.) Indian government just focused on making committees rather than to implement it. So, he conclude that laws should be implemented properly to control black money in our country.

CA Lalit Mohan Aggarwal (2012) edited the white paper on black money studied that violation of laws by central and state govt leads to criminal activities which in turn leads to generation of black money in Indian economy.

Arpit Guru and ShrutiKahaniJow (2010) researched on is black money income need for amendment in DTAA and ITEA analyzed that black money is spread everywhere in India up to large extent which continuously stashed towards abroad in a very large amount. They also studied how black money had caused menaces in our economy and in what ways it is used.

Table: 1 Recovery of Black Money Seized assets undisclosed income

Financial year	In Rs (Crore)	In Rs Crore
2015 -2016 up to November 2015	470	6,167
2014-2015	762	10,288
2013-2014	808	10,792
2012-2013	575	10,292
2011-2012	906	14,017
2010-2011	775	10,649
2009-2010	964	8,101

Source: Annual reports, Ministry of Finance.

Table1 clearly shows the limited abilities of the income Tax department when it comes to digging up black money in the economy. Even if we ignore this and assume that this around given

the government focus, the income tax department will be able to do better, the question is how much better.

The total amount of black money in the form of cash amounts to Rs 1.33 lakh crore. If the government can recover 55% of this, by taxing it, it amounts to around Rs.66000 crore.

The fall in GDP growth because of demonetization will turn out to be much greater than this. The centre for monitoring Indian economy estimates that just the transaction cost of demonetization will amount to Rs 1.28 lakh crore.

Genesis of black money Manipulation of Accounts for Tax Evasion

Remedies

One step alone cannot eradicate black economy, what needed is a joint effort at numerous levels. First of all, the political will is needed to curb the growth of Black money. Double taxation avoidance agreement (DTAA) and tax exchange information.

Agreement with tax haven countries will certainly help in bringing the capital flight problem. When we have sufficiently worked on the consciousness and trust issues we can look at the following reforms as a package because if handled individually, they will turn out to ineffective.

- Right information, judicial, bureaucracy and media reforms should be encouraged which will result in increase of transparency in the system. Also, building a special task force to enforce the laws effectively will go a long way.
- Simplification of the tax laws should be done as it will make it easy to catch those who are fudging the accounts.
- The link between the politicians and money power needs to be broken as this to the policy makers themselves resorting to sources for easy money.
- There should be three tier and interlinked representation in the legislatures on the same ground as party structures, which will increase the credibility of the contesting candidates.
- Increasing the accountability of institution and individuals and especially of the policy makers will act as big step in eradicating black economy in our country.
- Leaders and persons in position should file a return of their assets and incomes which should be subjected to scrutiny by a special agency created for this purpose.
- Lowering of tax rates so that tax evasion becomes unnecessary. Tendency to evade tax creeps in when tax rates are high.
- Controls, licenses and permits should be reduced to minimum. If necessary, they should be made available without under the table payments.
- As recommended by wanchoo committee, agriculture income should also be subjected to income tax as other incomes.
- Government should subsidize election expenditure of political parties as is done in West Germany.
- Heavy capital gains tax should be lowered.
- Registration fees in relation to property and other real estate should be lowered.
- All the tax laws should be revised so as to eliminate loopholes.
- Deterrent punishment must be given to those who are found guilty of profiteering, black-marketing and smuggling.

Impacts of black money on black economy

The effects of black money in a country are discussed under the following heads.

- False information about the economy

The most important effect of black money is provide false information about. The actual economy because it remains outside the purview of the economic policies. The presence of a sizeable black money casts doubts on the validity of the data on national income estimates, per capital income, and distribution of income, consumption, saving and investment.

- Impact on Fiscal system

Government is fully based on tax revenue. Evasion of taxes has serious consequences for the economy's fiscal system. Indirect taxes enquiry committee in this connection mentioned "Black money and tax evasion, which go hand in hand, have also the effect of seriously undermining the equity concept of taxation and warping its progressiveness. Together, they throw a greater burden to the economy.

Create inequalities

The black money creates inequalities among people. The excess of money leads to purchase non-essential articles, which gives demonstration effect. The overall consumption pattern is titled in favour of rich and elite classes.

- Misguiding on resource allocation

Black money distorts resource allocation in the economy and after leads to wasteful and often leads to wasteful use of money. It leads to conspicuous consumption and in turn results in the diversion of large funds to unproductive channels which ultimately put the economy out of order.

- Implications for monetary policy

The black money related to the stock of “black liquidity”. The stock of black liquidity is defined as the cumulating of black savings from black income in the form of cash and other readily convertible assets such as gold silver.

It is “black liquidity” which creates a lot of problems for monetary authorities to regulate the economy. The existence of sizable “black liquidity” in our country misguides the government to diverting credit from more urgent to the less urgent.

Suggestions

1. The majority of India’s black money must exist as cash in India. It cannot be sent overseas in very large amounts, since even the havalas route will mean that the rupees just change hands in India.
2. The RBI knows how much money it has printed up until now. The nation of India knows how much money is in the economy at the moment. Whatever the missing is the total volume of black money hidden away.
3. Black money revolves around in cash only so the government should put restriction on cash transactions wherever possible and intend should increase the use of plastic money like debit cards, credit cards etc., by other such means.
4. The government should not give absolute power of work to anyone person as it creates monopoly and instead should segregate the among many persons.
5. All the aspects of its generation should be looked into and stopped.
6. Competitive bids should be motivated.
7. However, we can decently quickly and massively clean up India’s economy through the above suggested method.

Conclusions

The fiscal system should be carefully watched and controlled by the RBI and the central government to control the problem of black money in India. The Government of India strictly follows the rules and regulations against the black income earners and tax evasion peoples. It will help to control the black money in India and it will help to overall development of the economy.

References

1. Dr.S.sankaran India economy first published 1972 Maugham publication Chennai-600 017.
2. Ruddar Datt, K.P.M.Sundaram fiftieth edition-2004 S.Chand & company Ltd, New Delhi. 110055.
3. Sukanta Sarkar (2010) “The parallel economy in India; causes, impact and government initiatives. Economic journal of development issues, volume 11 -12 no: (1 – 2) P 124 – 134.
4. CA Lalit Mohan Agarwal (2012), edit. “White paper on black money”. Journal of securities Academy and faculty for e-education. Vol – 72.